

White Paper

What the Numbers from My Dashboard Tell Me About South Asia Air Cargo: Revenue Dynamics, Yield Pressures, and the Istanbul - Dubai Corridor

Industry White Paper

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A Note on Where This Comes From

I have been looking at South Asia air cargo data from a desk in Dubai for about Eight years.

Every week, I build performance reports that track yield, revenue, capacity utilisation, and market trends across our network — covering markets from the UAE, Saudi Arabia, Kenya, Nigeria, India, and Pakistan etc. Every week, discussions and analysis of what is happening across the region and what it means commercially.

This white paper is, in many ways, an extension of that work — but written for a broader audience: Freight Professionals, Logistics Executives, Aviation Analysts, and anyone who wants to understand what is actually happening in South Asia air cargo right now, from the perspective of someone who works with the data every day.

The numbers I will reference, come from public industry sources. The interpretation comes from seven years of watching those numbers move and about 20 years in this industry across Singapore Airlines, DHL Global Forwarding, DB Schenker, and Turkish Airlines Cargo.

Abstract

In South Asia, encompassing India, Pakistan, Bangladesh and Sri Lanka, emerging as one of the most strategically important air cargo geographies of 2020s. India's international cargo volumes grew over 17% YOY in 2024–2025, and the country has set a national target of 10 million tons annual air cargo by

2030. Pakistan, smaller in scale but generates structurally flexible cargo flows driven by Textiles and Apparel exports, Agricultural products, and diaspora patterns that behave differently from general trade cargo and requires unique assessment approach. Bangladesh's Garment export dominance and growing rate volatility, and Sri Lanka's niche but high-yield perishable and apparel exports. Together, they form a diverse, fast-growing, and analytically complex region that requires looking beyond the average.

In this white paper, I analyse the South Asia air cargo market through the dual lens of revenue dynamics and yield pressure based on my seven years of analytical experience within Turkish Airlines Cargo team, based in Dubai. I further examine the strategic role of the Istanbul–Dubai connectivity axis in shaping South Asia cargo flows to Europe and beyond. The MoM and YoY trends, I track in our regional analytics dashboards tell us about the market trend.

1. India: The Market That Changed Everything

I remember when the India numbers started moving differently.

For years, India was a strong but predictable market, they had solid volumes, competitive rates, consistent seasonal patterns. Then, around the period of 2023–2024, something shifted significantly. The growth rate accelerated. E-commerce cargo started growing faster than General Freight. Pharmaceutical export volumes were already significant, entered a phase of compounded upward momentum. And the Government began real investment in air cargo infrastructure.

The data confirms what I was seeing in the dashboards. India's international air cargo volumes grew more than 17% year-on-year between April 2024 to January 2025. The country has committed USD 4.99 billion investment in Air Cargo, including Dedicated Cargo Terminals, Free Trade Zones, and Digital Tracking Infrastructure.

The national target of 10 million tons of Annual Productivity by 2030, represents approximately three times increase from the 3.26 million tons in 2024. That is not incremental growth but a Structural Transformation.

1.1 What Is Actually Driving It

Pharmaceuticals - TK's Anchor Commodity from India

India is one of the world's largest drug exporters, and air cargo is the only reliable mode for temperature-sensitive, time-critical cargo. For Turkish Airlines, India's pharmaceutical exports to Europe like Germany, Netherlands, UK are among our strongest performing commodity flows. Istanbul's SmartIST terminal has dedicated pharmaceutical areas and temperature-controlled cold storage zones built precisely for this cargo type. This is a lane where TK competes directly and effectively. A pharmaceutical shipment from Mumbai to Frankfurt via Istanbul is more competitive in time and cost, than routing through Dubai or Doha.

E-Commerce - The Fastest Growing Segment

India's online shopping population is growing rapidly. Turkish Airlines is launching a dedicated E-commerce facility at SmartIST in 2026, the Istanbul Hub is positioning for exactly this South Asia to

Europe E-com growth. Indian Fashion, Handicrafts, and Electronics destined for European consumers via Istanbul represent a genuine and growing commercial opportunity for TK.

Perishables - Seasonal but High-Yield

India's Mango exports during the April - June create a predictable increase in annual demand. Managing capacity ahead of mango season like planning the Allotments in place and the Pricing is one of the most commercially consequential decisions our Regional team makes each year.

1.2 What the MoM Data Tells Me

In my Power BI dashboards, India's seasonal MoM pattern is remarkably consistent year over year:

March - April: Sharp MoM uptick as perishable exports begin

September - October: Sustained MoM growth as Diwali e-commerce builds

November - December: YoY strength sustained by Christmas-oriented export shipments to Europe

January - February: MoM normalisation, the post-festive trough

The commercial team that positions capacity correctly ahead of the October surge captures high yield.

2. Pakistan: The Market Most Analyses Get Wrong

Pakistan deserves more attention in air cargo analysis.

Pakistan's cargo flows have a structure that is genuinely distinct and aligns particularly well with Turkish Airlines Cargo's network strengths.

Pakistan's textiles are among the world's largest export categories, to Europe i-e UK, Germany, Netherlands, France, Italy. The Spring-Summer buying season drives a January - March export peak; the Autumn - Winter season drives a September - October peak. These cycles are predictable and plannable. From Karachi and Lahore to European retail warehouses via Istanbul, TK is a genuinely competitive option.

Surgical Instruments and Pharmaceuticals

Sialkot's surgical instrument cluster is one of the world's largest exports of high-value, low-volume, yield-positive cargo to Europe and USA. From Karachi's pharmaceutical exports to Europe.

Both commodity types benefit from SmartIST's specialised handling facilities and TK's European distribution depth.

Diaspora Cargo - The Resilience Factor

Pakistan's large expatriate communities in the UAE, Saudi Arabia, Qatar, Kuwait, and the UK generate consistent Personal effects, Gift, and Food cargo flows regardless of economic conditions. During Eid, wedding season, and Pakistani holidays, diaspora cargo volumes spikes noticeably. These predictable movements help to plan capacity and yield in advance.

2.1 The Airspace Disruption: What Actually Happened

The India–Pakistan airspace closure in 2025 was the most significant operational disruption affected our South Asia network in recent years. It extended through multiple consecutive monthly renewals, and it has had real, measurable commercial consequences.

Turkish Airlines Cargo, whose Istanbul hub provides alternative routing paths, were better positioned to absorb the disruption.

This kind of disruption, a good analyst needs to be able to separate from structural market trends. The airspace closure was an operational disruption and it was important, but not representative of the underlying market trajectory.

3. Bangladesh: The Underrated Rate Story

Bangladesh is a market I watch closely in our dashboards because its cargo rate movements tend to be among the most dramatic in South Asia, and those movements have a logic that needs careful analysis.

Bangladesh is the world's 2nd largest Garment exporter after China, and its profile is dominated by one commodity which is Ready-made Garments (RMG) bound for European and North American fashion brands. H&M, Zara, Primark, M&S etc have market on a tight buying calendar.

The rate dynamics are distinctive during peak buying season. General cargo spot rates from Dhaka can move sharply. In early 2024, Bangladesh general cargo spot rates rose by approximately 40% in four weeks during a peak demand period, driven by strong apparel export demand. The market is sensitive, reactive, but with real-time visibility it is also full of yield opportunity.

Political turmoil in August 2024 caused a pause in international logistics. Again, a reminder that in emerging markets, there are always operational and commercial risks. The analyst watching MoM trends in Bangladesh needs to understand the country's political calendar as well as its commercial.

TK's Bangladesh Angle

For Bangladesh, Garment exports to Europe Fashion Hubs like Germany, UK, Netherlands etc, Istanbul routing is geographically efficient and commercially competitive. SmartIST with handling capacity of E-commerce and General cargo, positions TK well for Bangladesh's primarily textile-driven export profile.

4. Sri Lanka: Small Market, High Yield

Sri Lanka consistently delivers exceptional air cargo yields despite representing the smallest market by volume in region. The market has two primary export profiles:

Apparel and Textiles

Sri Lanka's garment industry, producing for premium European and American brands. Country generates export flows with similar seasonal rhythms to Bangladesh, but with a higher-value, more quality-focused

commodity profile. Sri Lankan apparel exports command better yield than volume-driven Bangladesh garment lanes because the products lean towards premium fashion rather than mass-market volume.

Perishables - Especially Tea and Seafood

Sri Lanka's export portfolio, dominated by Tea, Seafood, Spices relies on efficient airfreight connections to Europe. During 2024, a tight supply-demand imbalance caused cargo spot rates to surge by 55% within 4 weeks. The strongest rate movement of any South Asia market reflecting the dynamics of a small but high-quality market.

TK's Sri Lanka Position

Turkish Airlines serves Colombo through Istanbul. For Sri Lankan exporters targeting European markets especially German tea importers, UK fashion retailers, and Scandinavian seafood buyers. Istanbul routing provides competitive transit times and strong onward distribution reach very efficiently compared to the Gulf-routed alternatives.

5. Yield: The Number That Actually Matters

Volume growth is exciting. Yield is what pays the bills.

The global average air cargo yield reached USD 2.44/kg in 2025, at its lowest level since 2019. The third consecutive year of yield decline as pandemic-era capacity distortions have been normalised and competitive capacity already returned to the market.

On our South Asia lanes, the yield picture is more detailed than this global average suggests.

5.1 TK's Yield Position — The Long-Haul Advantage

I want to be direct about something that matters for accurate yield analysis of Turkish Airlines Cargo's South Asia network.

TK is not the dominant carrier on short-haul South Asia to Gulf lanes.

Turkish Airlines Cargo's yield advantage in South Asia is on the long-haul lanes to Europe, USA, and Africa via Istanbul. On these lanes, Istanbul is the most geographically efficient routing available from South Asia to Europe destinations. A pharmaceutical shipment from Mumbai to Frankfurt via Istanbul is shorter in distance and faster in total transit than routing via Middle East.

The yield, I track on these lanes reflects those structural advantages:

- i. Less exposure to the Price aggressive Gulf corridor,
- ii. Stronger position on Europe-bound premium cargo, and the benefit of Istanbul's unmatched distribution depth

Over 125 European destinations served from a single Hub.

5.2 Commodity Mix - The Yield Protection Strategy

Across all four South Asia markets, the pattern I observe in my yield analysis is consistent: commodity mix is the most reliable yield protection mechanism in my opinion.

Market	High-Yield Commodity	TK Lane Strength
India	Pharmaceuticals, Perishables	India–Europe via IST
Pakistan	Surgical instruments, Textiles	Pakistan–Europe via IST
Bangladesh	Premium RMG, E-commerce	Bangladesh–Europe via IST
Sri Lanka	Tea, Seafood, Premium apparel	Sri Lanka–Europe via IST

When pharmaceutical and perishable cargo share is high on a lane, yield holds stronger even under competitive pressure. When general cargo dominates, yield compresses. Managing the commodity mix for example, prioritising high-margin cargo types within available capacity, is the practical yield management lever that data analytics makes visible and actionable.

5.3 Dynamic Pricing: Where the Industry Is Going

During my time at DB Schenker managing complex RFQs for clients like Siemens, GE, Huawei, and Adidas, pricing was largely a static process. The market is moving away from this model.

Multi-airline marketplace platforms are growing rapidly where rates are set dynamically based on real-time capacity and demand signals. In my Power BI work, I see the indications to this already: the correlation between load factor movements and subsequent rate adjustments on our South Asia lanes is measurable and consistent. The commercial team that can act on that signal faster, can capture the yield.

6. The Istanbul–Dubai Axis: Correcting the Narrative

From my desk in Dubai, I work within what I think of as the most strategically important cargo corridor for MEASA long-haul trade: the Istanbul–Dubai axis.

But I want to correct a common misunderstanding about how this axis actually works for South Asia cargo — one that I think matters for accurate commercial analysis.

Dubai is the primary cargo hub in Middle East, processing 2.8 million tonnes in 2024, an 18.5% year-on-year increase. For South Asia cargo bound for the Gulf and African markets, Dubai is the natural aggregation and distribution point. Its geographic proximity to South Asian origins makes it the first-leg hub of choice for Gulf and African destined cargo.

Istanbul, as the most internationally connected airport in Europe and serving over 330 destinations through 116 airline partners. Istanbul is not primarily a South Asia to Gulf hub but South Asia to Europe,

Americas, and Africa hub. The Istanbul - Dubai pairing works not as a relay for Gulf traffic, but as a dual-hub system where Dubai handles regional distribution and Istanbul handles intercontinental reach.

For South Asia shippers targeting European markets that means India's Pharmaceutical exporters, Pakistan's Textile manufacturers, Bangladesh's Garment producers, and Sri Lanka's Tea and Seafood exporters - the Istanbul routing is often the most commercially rational choice. Not because it is cheap. Because for European final destinations, it is direct, fast, and served by a network of onward connections that no single-hub Gulf carrier can match.

What the Month-on-Month and Year-on-Year data in my dashboards consistently shows, is the resilience of this corridor. Its ability to maintain volume and yield through disruptions that affect other routing options, coming from network depth at both ends. When the India - Pakistan airspace closure affected other carriers, Istanbul's alternative connectivity provided a flexibility that competitors could not offer.

7. What I Expect to See in the Data Over the Next 12 Months

Indian volumes will continue their structural upward growth. The Government Investment, the E-commerce, and the Pharmaceutical export expansion are structural, not cyclical. The YoY comparisons in our dashboards will continue to show strong growth on India–Europe lanes via Istanbul.

Pakistan volumes will recover after Political stability. Pakistan's underlying cargo demand like Textiles, Surgical instruments, Diaspora flows — remains structurally intact and growing.

Bangladesh will remain the region's most rate-volatile market. Its garment export concentration creates predictable seasonal spikes and acute sensitivity to domestic disruption. For commercial teams with real-time data visibility, that volatility is as much opportunity as risk.

Sri Lanka will punch above its weight on yield. Small volume, high quality, strong commodity mix — Sri Lanka will continue generating yield metrics that outperform its tonnage contribution on South Asia regional dashboards.

TK's long-haul South Asia position will be strengthened. As SmartIST's capacity expands toward 4.5 million tonnes and the dedicated E-commerce facility launch in 2026. Turkish Airlines Cargo has strong ability to handle South Asia's growing Europe-bound cargo flows like Pharmaceuticals, Textiles, E-commerce, Perishables will continue improving.

8. Conclusion: What the Dashboard Cannot Tell You — and What It Can

I have spent this white paper discussing what the data shows. I want to end with something the data cannot show.

Air cargo is not just a logistics function. It is an infrastructure and connective tissue that keeps global supply chains working, gets Pharmaceutical medicines to patients in Germany, delivers Bangladeshi

Garments to European retailers, moves Pakistani Mangoes to diaspora families in the UK, and ensures Sri Lankan tea arrives fresh on Scandinavian shelves.

The numbers in my Power BI dashboards capture some of this. Month-on-Month and Year-on-Year trends, yield variances, load factors, commodity mix, these are the language of commercial management, and they are genuinely useful for making better decisions.

But behind every data point is a shipment. Behind every shipment is a business that needed something moved, a supply chain that depended on it arriving on time, a customer whose expectations were either met or not.

After 20 years in this industry, I have learned to keep this in mind when I look at the numbers. The data is just the starting point. Truly understanding what it means for the businesses and regions that rely on these trade lanes is something no dashboard can fully automate.

This is the most important part of cargo analytics, and it is the work I do every day.

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